

PROFESSIONAL TASKS OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL TEXTS AT FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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ELSEVIER

Suyarova Shahnoza Toylokovna

teacher Department of Languages
of Tashkent State Agrarian University
Uzbekistan, Tashkent

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Abstract: The article examines the study of the cognitive bases of vocabulary selection in the formation of scientific and technical texts in English. For the formation of scientific and technical texts in English, they should be classified taking into account the pragmatic attitude of the researcher.

Keywords: English language, scientific and technical, text, vocabulary, formation, research, pragmatic attitude

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

If we encounter a scientific-technical text in linguistic literature, its author, as a rule, is a scientist who conducts experimental research and / or develops a described scientific-technical concept. Also, a scientific-technical text that presents the results of scientific research to a wide audience is often a scientific-technical text during the research - a result that is not directly related to scientific research.

Studying the authorship of modern scientific and technical texts allows us to say that both scientists and writers can write them. For example, scientific and technical books of Bill Bryson and writer Hannah Holmes, articles and lectures of chemist Alexei Paevsky, works of biologist A. V. Markov, blogs of Alexei Vodovozov, Ilya Kabanov, articles of astrophysicist Sergey Popov, etc.[3]

During the research, the reaction to the achievements of science, but also the reaction of the society to science, to the profession of scientists as a whole, depends on the education of the scientific public, its ability to deliver scientific information to the ordinary student in high quality. People want to know the essence of scientific information as accurately as possible, therefore, the talent of a scientific journalist plays an important role in presenting scientific material. The contradiction of a scientific-popular text is that, on the one hand, it should be figurative, bright, understandable and understandable, and on the other hand, it should remain scientific. "By overcoming this contradiction, the author of a scientific and technical text solves a problem no less than the creation of a scientific text, and sometimes even more difficult."

The problem of scientific popularization in Russia is raised by many well-known scientific journalists. In particular, in the field of science and technology, you can count with your fingers the real professionals in the field of scientific journalism, who set a high level in terms of the quality of scientific and technical material presented by prestigious scientific publications.

A scientific researcher must be able to distinguish true academic knowledge from pseudo-scientific knowledge and use the correct language techniques to interpret it correctly for the general public who are not narrow specialists in any scientific field. In order to make scientific knowledge understandable to non-specialists, scientific journalists, as well as famous scientists, there is a risk of distorting scientific information in order to achieve their goals, because the process of adaptation of academic knowledge, as a rule, requires a journalist. abandoning some highly specialized terms, as well as popular explanations of complex scientific phenomena and discussions of their relationships. "Firstly, scientific journalism is related to scientific knowledge and the principles of its transmission, secondly, it belongs to the normative and practical field of journalism as a profession, thirdly, scientific journalists act as mediators between the scientific community and the general public. "

The abstractness and abstractness of scientific concepts encourages the authors of scientific and technical works to use allegories, metaphors, comparisons, which by their nature cannot replace a rigorous scientific presentation, which creates linguistic difficulties in translating a scientific text into a popular text. science format. Therefore, many scientists reject a scientific and technical text that introduces students to their scientific conclusions and rules.

Speaking about the processing of scientific information, journalists note that not every science is popular. In particular, this applies to mathematics and other forms of abstract knowledge, where it is problematic to find an appropriate metaphor and create an interesting story around the topic of the article.

Most of the journalists working in the field of science claim that the scientific text will become popular and interesting at the same time. [4]

The influence of the Internet on the process of popularization of science is now recognized: "Anyone can pick up a keyboard and communicate to the entire world about science." On the one hand, this allows people who are interested in science, but who are not science journalists, to share high-quality material on the global network. On the other hand, there is a negative impact of the Internet on the quality of work of journalists. In their work, they often focus on finding sensational news, rather than on their own research and understanding of a scientific problem. "In consequence, readers are receiving a distorted image of science as a series of "discoveries" and "breakthroughs"". Moreover, journalists visit the same sites, use

the Internet editions of the same scientific journals as a source for writing popular science articles. Thus, the range of topics covered by journalist's narrows, and the variety of problems discussed is lost.[3]

It also discusses the fact that journalists working in the scientific field set a priori the goal of attracting the attention of the reader, neglecting the correct presentation of scientific material. In this regard, English-language authors are often criticized for presenting facts in the style of infotainment, meaning that the entertaining function of a popular science text is exaggerated.

The popular science journals and media publications that we used as sources of linguistic material tend to turn to highly qualified authors, both professional scientists and professional journalists. The study of the principles of vocabulary choice, which are used by the authors of English-language popular science articles, can contribute to solving the problems mentioned above, which indicates the relevance of our study.

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